

D3.3 SOCIAL INNOVATORS FACTSHEETS

WP3 Open innovation challenge for
social impact

 POSITIVE

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project number:	101096390
Project acronym:	POSITIVE
Project title:	Participatory Open Social Innovation Through Interlinking Valuable Ecosystems
Instrument:	HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02
Start date of project:	01.02.2023
Duration:	22 months

DELIVERABLE INFO

Deliverable title:	Social Innovators Factsheets
Work package:	WP3 Open innovation challenge for social impact
Due date of deliverable:	30.06.2024
Deliverable lead:	HIT
Deliverable type:	R - Document, report
Dissemination level:	PU - Public
Version:	Final Version

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
1.0		Beatrice Devigili (HIT)	First Draft
1.1	10.06.2024	Nicola Doppio (HIT)	Amendements
1.2	18.06.2024	Beatrice Devigili (HIT)	Amendements
1.3	20.06.2024	Vivien Riener (GH)	Proof reading and review
1.4	21.06.2024	Elisa Poletti (TST)	Proof reading and review
1.5	23.06.2024	Nicola Doppio (HIT)	Proof reading and review
Final Version	27.06.2024	Mirjam Zillober, Miljana Cosic (SEZ)	Final formatting, submission

DISCLAIMER

This document reflects only the authors' view. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Table of contents

Executive Summary.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
1.1. POSITIVE Project.....	4
1.2. The POSITIVE Impact Challenge	4
1.3. How to read this deliverable.....	6
2. Challenge projects hosted in Italy	8
Factsheet 1 - Mobile app for monitoring work integration projects.....	8
Factsheet 2 - Upgrading “domotic” tech for people with disabilities	9
Factsheet 3 - Tracking people connections and their value.....	10
Factsheet 4 - A digital diary for the nursery’s families	11
Factsheet 5 - Connecting care: a comprehensive tech solution.....	12
3. Challenge projects hosted in Germany	13
Factsheet 1 - Platform for talent training & matching.....	13
Factsheet 2 - Enhancing a mobile app for neighbourly help	14
Factsheet 3 - Mobile app for scheduling appointments between people with hearing impairments and sign language interpreters.....	15
Factsheet 4 - Booking tool for schools	16
Factsheet 5 – Mobile app for better inclusion at work.....	17
4. Challenge projects hosted in Lithuania	18
Factsheet 1 - Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania	18
Factsheet 2 - Textale one stop shop	19
Factsheet 3 - Digital Band.....	20
Factsheet 4 - Easy Count.....	21
Factsheet 5 - “SP Club” Beneficiary Relations & Impact Management.....	22

List of tables

Table 1. Factsheet 1 - Italy	8
Table 2. Factsheet 2 - Italy	9
Table 3. Factsheet 3 - Italy	10
Table 4. Factsheet 4 - Italy	11
Table 5. Factsheet 5 – Italy	12
Table 6. Factsheet 1 - Germany	13
Table 7. Factsheet 2 - Germany	14
Table 8. Factsheet 3 - Germany	15
Table 9. Factsheet 4 - Germany	16
Table 10. Factsheet 5 - Germany	17
Table 11. Factsheet 1 - Lithuania	18
Table 12. Factsheet 2 - Lithuania	19
Table 13. Factsheet 3 - Lithuania	20
Table 14. Factsheet 4 - Lithuania	21
Table 15. Factsheet 5 - Lithuania	22

Abbreviations

DS	Design Sprint
GH	Grünhof
HIT	Hub Innovazione Trentino
HQ	Head Quarter
LIC	Lithuanian Innovation Centre
LiSVA	Lithuanian Social Business Association
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OIC	Open Innovation Challenge
PM	Project management
SB2G	Social Business to Government
SE	Social Entrepreneurship
SEZ	Steinbeis Europa Zentrum
SI	Social Innovation
SO	Social Organization
TST	Trentino Social Tank
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document presents the projects hosted at the three editions of the **Positive Impact Challenge (PIC)**, a pivotal initiative under the POSITIVE Project aiming at supporting digital product and service innovation in social businesses utilizing an Open Innovation approach.

Implemented between February and April 2024 across Germany, Italy, and Lithuania, this Open Innovation Challenge aimed to support a minimum of 5 social entrepreneurs and social businesses in each participating country in better designing and innovating their products, services and processes utilizing Design Thinking methods (e.g. the Design Sprint).

Funded through the HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02 call, the project emphasizes the critical integration of social and technological innovation to drive impactful societal advancements and the possibility to achieve them by means of Open Innovation methods.

This deliverable contains **15 factsheets** detailing the descriptions of the challenges (or problems) that were submitted to the PICs by the participating social enterprises, as well as the innovative solutions developed by teams of young talents that played the role of so-called Solvers. These factsheets are also published on the project website, including specific pictures taken from the teams addressing the project (www.positivechallenge.eu).

To know more about the process of setting up and implementing the PICs in the three countries, please see D3.2 – Report on POSITIVE Impact Challenges including retrospect.

1. Introduction

1.1. POSITIVE Project

The POSITIVE project (Participatory Open Social Innovation Through Interlinking Valuable Ecosystems) focuses on raising awareness about the benefits of social innovation and providing capacity building about social innovation and social entrepreneurship (SE) to the tech innovation ecosystem. It seeks to support SE, foster inclusivity, and facilitate digital transformation through the implementation of an Open Innovation Challenge across three countries, the so called POSITIVE Impact Challenge. The project aims to **strengthen both ecosystems** through cross-fertilization, knowledge exchange, and policy recommendations for replicating the POSITIVE Impact Challenge model on regional and European levels, ultimately fostering a more resilient tech innovation ecosystem capable of addressing societal challenges.

The project involves **six partners** from three different countries: Italy, Germany, and Lithuania. Each country contributes one partner from the tech sector and one from the social innovation sector, ensuring a balanced and comprehensive approach to achieving the project's goals.

Partners are:

- Germany
 - Tech Innovation Partner: Steinbeis Europa Zentrum (SEZ)
 - Social Innovation Partner: Grünhof e.V. (GH)
- Italy
 - Tech Innovation Partner: Fondazione Hub Innovazione Trentino (HIT)
 - Social Innovation Partner: Trentino Social Tank (TST)
- Lithuania
 - Social Innovation Partner: Lithuanian Innovation Centre (LIZ)
 - Social innovation Partner: Lithuanian Social Business Association (LISVA)

1.2. The POSITIVE Impact Challenge

The POSITIVE project dedicates a whole section (WP3 – Open Innovation Challenge for Social Impact) to developing and putting into action the **Positive Impact Challenge model**, an Open Innovation initiative designed specifically to foster social innovation. Initially adapted from the UX Challenge format, the model was iterated and improved through collaborative efforts among the

POSITIVE

project partners. This iterative process included a comprehensive 2-day workshop and subsequent online training sessions and personalized consultations facilitated by HIT. Following the finalization of the model, the focus turned to **knowledge transfer**, transitioning the final methodology to consortium partners, equipping them with the necessary insights and competencies to independently execute the Challenges. All the essential operational details were consolidated into the **Partner's Challenge Handbook (D3.1)**, making sure that the model was well-documented and ready for successful use.

Central to WP3's objectives was the execution of three distinct POSITIVE Impact Challenges across different partner countries. These challenges were specifically designed not only to promote Open Innovation practices but also to foster impactful social outcomes within each respective region. Social Innovation (SI) partners took the lead in organizing and executing the challenge locally with a great help from the tech partners which also participated at the operative level and provided important strategic advice according to their previous experience in managing an edition of the UX Challenges in Europe¹.

The organization of each Challenge involved key stakeholders within the social sector, primarily social businesses and cooperatives acting as problem owners, the so called **Seekers**. University students with diverse backgrounds such as computer science, economics, innovation management, psychology, sociology, information technology and UX design have been engaged in the development of solutions for these problems. In the terminology of open innovation, they are known as **Solvers**. Guided by mentors with expertise in design thinking, agile project management, service design, innovation management, and digital technologies, the Solvers applied the Design Sprint method. Their objective was to develop innovative concepts, ranging from product mock-ups and customer journey maps to service blueprints and validated business models. These solutions were tested and refined with input from citizens, who represented the users of the proposed innovations.

For deeper insights into the POSITIVE Impact Challenge model and its implementation details, consult deliverables D3.1 – Partners' challenge Handbook and D3.2 - Report on POSITIVE Impact Challenges including retrospect. These documents provide comprehensive information on

¹ HIT, SEZ and LIC has been partner of the project H2020 INNOSUP-06 CSA, named "200SMEchallenge", whose aim was to enable six other innovation agencies (beyond HIT) to set up and replicate the UX Challenge in their own premises

how the model was created and the organization of the challenges, offering valuable insights into their development and execution.

1.3. How to read this deliverable

This report describes the fifteen challenges addressed in the three PIC editions. These PICs took place in Italy, Germany, and Lithuania between February and April of 2024, lasted between 3 and 8 days.

Each edition of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge hosted five to six “challenges”, or small projects, meaning coordinated teamwork efforts between Seekers (social businesses), Solvers (university students) and Mentors, that endured between three to five days. The Solvers have been divided into teams, each of them addressing a specific challenge with the aim of improving or innovating the value and the user experience of digital products, services or processes owned by the Seekers. Each of these teams used the Design Sprint methodology and delivered different tangible outputs such as prototypes, mockups, service blueprints, customer journey maps, or click dummies.

This report provides detailed insights into the fifteen challenges and their outcomes, presented per country. It clarifies the value proposition and potential impact of the POSITIVE Impact Challenge, while highlighting what types of projects, problems or opportunities are appropriate to be addressed with this methodology.

The report is divided into three main sections, each presenting five distinct challenges per country. Within each section, the outcomes of the challenges are systematically presented in a table format to ensure clarity and ease of reference.

Each challenge table includes the following details:

- **Description of the Seeker**
 - **Name:** The name of the organization or individual that owns the challenge aka. the Seeker
 - **Website:** The official website of the Seeker.
 - **Type of Entity:** The nature of the Seeker’s organization (e.g., non-profit, governmental, private sector).
 - **Mission:** The primary goals and objectives of the Seeker.
 - **Contact Person:** The individual responsible for communication regarding the challenge posed in the PIC.

POSITIVE

- **Description of the Challenge:** A detailed explanation of the challenge, outlining the problem it aims to address and the context in which it was set.
- **Next Steps:**
 - **How the Results Can Be Improved:** Suggestions and strategies for enhancing the outcomes of the challenge.
 - **Implementation by the Seeker:** Information on whether the results will be adopted and utilized by the Seeker.
- **Impact:** An analysis of the significance of the prototype or idea obtained from the PIC for the Seeker. This includes potential benefits, advancements, and implications for future work.

These factsheets were conceived for facilitating dissemination: they are also published on the project website: www.positivechallenge.eu

2. Challenge projects hosted in Italy

Factsheet 1 - Mobile app for monitoring work integration projects

SEEKER	NAME: ALPI	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: www.coop-alpi.it	CONTACT: Elisa Poletti
	MISSION: ALPI, which stands for "Avviamento al Lavoro su Progetti Individualizzati" (<i>Initiation to Work through Individualized Projects</i>), is a social cooperative enterprise that has been offering employment insertion pathways in Trentino since 1990.	
	TARGET GROUPS: People in vulnerable circumstances.	
CHALLENGE	To improve the User Experience of the MIO TUTOR Application , along with increasing its usability and utility. The App is a tool currently used within the cooperative by operators and team leaders to facilitate, streamline, and make observations, monitoring, and evaluation of employment insertion projects more objective.	
SOLUTION	The team of the challenge investigated reasons for scarce utilization of the app and identified usability and utility issues (mention product); it redesigned its main information architecture and user flows and delivered an interactive prototype on Figma.	
NEXT STEPS	ALPI is currently searching for project partners (designer + developer) and resources to refine the delivered prototype and developing a new version of the app.	
IMPACT	The use of the new app will allow the company to completely track the process of integration of a disadvantaged worker, and with that to better manage the process, report and account for yearly KPIs and achievement to the service owner (Public Services) and to explore artificial intelligence driven solutions (e.g., DSS). The app will also allow the tutor to focus on his coaching role.	

Table 1. Factsheet 1 - Italy

Factsheet 2 - Upgrading “domotic” tech for people with disabilities

SEEKER	NAME: CS4	TYPE: Social Cooperative (type A)
	URL: https://www.cs4.coop/	CONTACT: Novella Eccel
	MISSION: Non-profit social cooperative founded in 1988, dedicated to providing daily support to people with disabilities and their families.	
	TARGET GROUPS: People with disabilities	
CHALLENGE	The cooperative helps people with disabilities to achieve housing autonomy, through “domotic” flats. Yet, the current technology (a wall screen) is outdated and unused. CS4 asked the team to replace it with a mobile app for easier, portable daily activities via smartphones.	
SOLUTION	Prior to prototyping, operator interviews informed the design process. User personas and scenarios were developed from the insights gathered. The proposed mobile app “Abitare” features separate interfaces for occupants and operators and syncs data with existing Microsoft accounts used by the cooperative.	
NEXT STEPS	The application can be developed by leveraging Microsoft Office APIs. The project aligns with the interests of other cooperatives operating in similar fields, and our intention is to collectively apply for national funding opportunities that support such initiatives.	
IMPACT	Reduction of service-related costs, a better integration with users’ daily routines and the possibility to remotely manage and update to do lists and calendars.	

Table 2. Factsheet 2 - Italy

Factsheet 3 - Tracking people connections and their value

SEEKER	NAME: IMPACT HUB TRENTINO	TYPE: Social Enterprise
	URL: https://trento.impacthub.net/	CONTACT: Matteo Milani
	MISSION: Impact Hub Trentino offers coworking space for freelancers and companies, along with networking opportunities. It provides business consultancy for startups and SMEs and organizes projects and events to foster connections in the entrepreneurial and social ecosystem.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Freelancers, start-ups, small businesses, entrepreneurs.	
CHALLENGE	Create a tool that effectively tracks, enhances and quantifies interactions among hubbers while considering potential business and social impacts, as well as feasibility and profitability.	
SOLUTION	The proposed solution integrates NFC technology with the Community Wall (physical place in the Hub), enabling hubbers to monitor interactions seamlessly. This digitized process streamlines connection-building while maintaining the valued physical interaction within the community, fostering a vibrant atmosphere.	
NEXT STEPS	Impact Hub will look for feasible ways to implement the solution.	
IMPACT	The Challenge itself, thanks to the fresh perspective of students, prompts reflections on the company, leading to a reevaluation of its organizational structure.	

Table 3. Factsheet 3 - Italy

Factsheet 4 - A digital diary for the nursery's families

SEEKER	NAME: LA COCCINELLA	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: https://www.lacoccinella.coop/	CONTACT: Lorenzo De Preto
	MISSION: La Coccinella builds opportunities and services for children and families, collaborating with local institutions and other organizations to support community growth.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Children 0-16 years and their families	
CHALLENGE	To design a diary application (EduMapp) that allows parents to track their children's development.	
SOLUTION	The team solution consists of four sections: " Discover " digitizes "La Coccinella" newspaper. " Nursery " shares nursery communications. " Personal " delivers tailored messages with pinned info. " Services " lists available services and contacts.	
NEXT STEPS	There's a strong interest in advancing the digital communication aspect, such as the Journal La Coccinella.	
IMPACT	Families could have an instrument to connect with near-based experts, then be better supported in their role. La Coccinella could position itself as a reference for all families (not only the ones using its nurseries).	

Table 4. Factsheet 4 - Italy

Factsheet 5 - Connecting care: a comprehensive tech solution

SEEKER	NAME: LA RETE	TYPE: Social Cooperative
	URL: https://la-rete.mailchimpsites.com/	CONTACT: Nicholas Moser
	MISSION: Since 1988, La Rete has been working with and for people with disabilities and their families to improve their quality of life, recognizing the community as a crucial place for social inclusion.	
	TARGET GROUPS: people with disabilities, their families and the community where they live.	
CHALLENGE	The organization wants to enhance user engagement through innovative website features . With profiles accessible to families, social workers, and administrators, our aim is to streamline communication, optimize tools, and centralize information.	
SOLUTION	The solution consists of a mobile app for operators, parents, and volunteers, along with a web app for operators. The operator's app includes an activity calendar, report submission, absence reporting, social folder access, and a photo archive. The parent's app offers activity tracking, contact lists, and document storage. The volunteer's app features note-taking, a photo archive, and activity booking.	
NEXT STEPS	Some students are exploring the project in their thesis. La Rete wants to develop the mobile app and is looking for resources that could support this phase.	
IMPACT	Sharp reduction in operator's time spent on phone calls or emailing to organize user activities will lead to more time spent directly with users and a better service offered.	

Table 5. Factsheet 5 – Italy

3. Challenge projects hosted in Germany

Factsheet 1 - Platform for talent training & matching

SEEKER	NAME: TechBloomz	TYPE: Social Startup
	URL: https://techbloomz.com/	CONTACT: Lena Leis
	MISSION: With every match of tech talents to tech companies, TechBloomz commits to support single mum's in Colombia to leverage their careers. TechBloom offers them access to bootcamps and daycare so that they can generate an income.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Single mothers with low income in Colombia / countries of the Global South.	
CHALLENGE	Development of a part of the TechBloomz placement platform: interface for companies seeking, training and hiring IT professionals. This interface will be crucial for establishing and maintaining transformative relationships between the the future employees and employers.	
SOLUTION	The solvers designed the sign-in-page of the matching platform for companies, where they can contribute to the development of the training content. They created a catalogue showing the trainees and their individual skills and training courses they are taking to facilitate the matching between company and trainee.	
NEXT STEPS	The next steps are not yet finalized, as it is currently still too early, and the design would have to be significantly adapted.	
IMPACT	The use of the new sign-in-page can be used for demo pitches for companies. Also, the challenge was a great opportunity for the Seeker to get to know new talents and to learn more about what's technically feasible.	

Table 6. Factsheet 1 - Germany

Factsheet 2 - Enhancing a mobile app for neighbourly help

SEEKER	NAME: HILVER	TYPE: Social StartUp
	URL: www.hilver.de	CONTACT: Nicolas Walter
	MISSION: HILVER offers a platform to volunteer and help older people with everyday tasks on the one hand, and to make use of help as a person in need of support on the other.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Senior citizens and other people in need of support; volunteers who help them.	
CHALLENGE	Users of the HILVER app, both those seeking and those providing help, should be encouraged to use it more intensively. Above all, older people should lose their fear of contact with the app and, secondly, helpers should accept more orders.	
SOLUTION	The solver team suggested merging the two existing Hilver apps (one for persons seeking, one for persons offering help) into one, thereby decreasing the confusion of users. Secondly, they proposed “Onboarding Events” for Seniors to reduce fear of contact. Thirdly, they introduced the AI-Assistant “HILVA” to lead users through the app. Lastly, a filter-function, reward system and gamification enhanced the user experience and engagement.	
NEXT STEPS	The first solution (web version) is almost complete. The other ideas (registration, filter function) are next on the priority list. The plan is not to implement the ideas one-to-one, as work is still required to integrate them into the existing product or to refine them.	
IMPACT	It is emphasized that these ideas would not have been developed without the incentive of the students and represent a significant enrichment . In general, there is a high level of satisfaction with the quality , and it is stated that expectations have been exceeded. Initial feedback on the web version has been extremely positive , which further strengthens confidence in the product.	

Table 7. Factsheet 2 - Germany

Factsheet 3 - Mobile app for scheduling appointments between people with hearing impairments and sign language interpreters

SEEKER	NAME: OnDa	TYPE: Social Startup
	URL: www.bfk.one	CONTACT: Fabian Hatwagner
	MISSION: Breaking down communication barriers for hearing-impaired and deaf-blind people and to developing solutions together with other associations, self-help groups and companies	
	TARGET GROUPS: Hearing-impaired and sign language interpreters	
CHALLENGE	Everyday communication between hearing, hearing-impaired and deaf-blind people often requires translation by sign language interpreters. A digital booking system for in-person translation services should make it easier and more flexible to find and book appointments.	
SOLUTION	The solver team developed an All-In-One App that features standardized and organized appointment scheduling with two interfaces: one for interpreters and one for the hearing impaired, which is specifically inclusively designed.	
NEXT STEPS	The next aim is to implement a billing function. Invoice templates are to be stored, accessibility ensured, and interpreter profiles implemented. Also, an optional function is to save specific interpreters as “favorites” that along with the option to create series of appointments should improve the user experience in the future.	
IMPACT	This solution might be the first in Europe: Around 70 million people in Europe live with hearing impairments.	

Table 8. Factsheet 3 - Germany

Factsheet 4 - Booking tool for schools

SEEKER	NAME: pro familia	TYPE: Welfare association
	URL: www.profamilia.de/fachinfos/fachveranstaltungen	CONTACT: Eva Rebholz
	MISSION: Early sexual education has been proven to prevent individual and social problems. pro familia offers needs-oriented, individualized and professional workshops for schools.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Schools (teachers)	
CHALLENGE	An online booking tool is intended to make it easier for schools to book appointments and put together customized content (modular principle from the pro familia's offers). The aim is to make booking easier, faster and clearer. This should save internal resources.	
SOLUTION	The solver team developed a click dummy for a booking tool for both target groups: teachers and the pro familia employees . It includes the choice of offers, scheduling of appointments, booking section, and invoicing.	
NEXT STEPS	Implement the concept of the problem solution by finding a way to apply the desired functions using the basic MS office package. This will make the solution scalable and applicable in all sites without requiring extra software.	
IMPACT	The click dummy itself produced by the team is less important, as it mainly represents an implementation option. The concept of the problem solution behind it has a much greater value from the organisation's perspective. As a social organization with little money available for IT, pro familia are dependent on support. Taking part in a hackathon can be a great solution to this problem.	

Table 9. Factsheet 4 - Germany

Factsheet 5 – Mobile app for better inclusion at work

SEEKER	NAME: Initiative für Mehrsprachigkeit und Bildung IMIB e.V.	TYPE: Social organization
	URL: https://imib-freiburg.de/	CONTACT: Nikoleta Wittmer
	MISSION: To promote multilingualism as an educational resource, especially in Baden-Württemberg where 40% of children are multilingual but heritage languages lack recognition. The goal is to identify and highlight organizations offering heritage language services for children and youth in Freiburg.	
	TARGET GROUPS: (1) Schools, providers of heritage language services, educational professionals and educational stakeholders who would like to recruit resources; (2) Multilingual families who need local services and general background information on multilingualism.	
CHALLENGE	The “ HSU Platform ” as a digital overview of multilingual offers for kids and young people in Freiburg is to be optimized and embedded in the existing IMIB website . The UX is to be improved for those seeking and providing services.	
SOLUTION	The solvers proposed optimizing the website for mobile devices to enhance the user experience on smartphones and tablets. They also recommended making older posts visible and made many links clickable to improve navigation. To further improve usability, the database should be integrated with the homepage, to making content more seamlessly accessible and increasing overall accessibility.	
NEXT STEPS	The range of services should be expanded , and the registration process optimized. Additionally, the database should be translated in multiple languages to reach a wider audience. The next steps include developing and implementing an advertising strategy to reach the target group . To this end, contacts with schools will be established and maintained, while the website will be revised.	
IMPACT	The mission of “IMIB” will be much better fulfilled if all the proposed solutions and next steps are implemented, as more people will be able to use the website and database more intuitively and easily.	

Table 10. Factsheet 5 - Germany

4. Challenge projects hosted in Lithuania

Factsheet 1 - Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania

SEEKER	NAME: Būk su manimi & Dirbinyčia	TYPE: viešoji įstaiga (Nonprofit; VšĮ)
	URL: https://www.facebook.com/Buk.su.manimi	CONTACT: Almante & Jolita
	MISSION: Significant reduction of textile waste (tons of textiles given a new life as attractive and useful products). Contribute to reduction of numbers of lonely elderly people, engage and integrate communities. Provide access to affordable, attractive goods made from recycled or renewed materials.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Marginalized/vulnerable people in the local community; consumers.	
CHALLENGE	Create a tool for charting faster and more efficient route, saving fuel and reducing CO2 emissions and using time more efficiently, during collection of discarded textiles, as well as household items within a 200-300 km radius from the town of Mazeikiai (Seeker's HQ).	
SOLUTION	A digital solution, Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania, to enable consistent routing: SE enters data (date and time for pick-up, number of textiles & other items to be collected, phone # & address) and receives route suggestion and fuel calculations depending on the vehicle they intend to use.	
NEXT STEPS	To perfect "Green Logistics of Northern Lithuania", the solution could be integrated with the SE's social media account where textile recollection requests are received on a regular basis, namely a bit of automation instead of manual entry of data.	
IMPACT	The specific impact of the innovation will be on smoother operations by the SE Būk su manimi & Dirbinyčia: specifically, digitalization and greening of SE's operations. Meanwhile, the overall societal impact will be the transformation of beliefs, habits and practices through education, engagement of youth, integration of the elderly, community creation and reduction of consumerism.	

Table 11. Factsheet 1 - Lithuania

Factsheet 2 - Textale one stop shop

SEEKER	NAME: TEXTALE (Resursai tvariai plėtrai)	TYPE: nonprofit organization
	URL: https://textale.lt/	CONTACT: Viktorija Nausėdė
	MISSION: Eliminate textile waste. "TEXTALE" is a fashion resale and exchange platform that invites you to buy, sell or donate non-wearable but stylish and high-quality clothing, accessories, footwear and home textiles.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Residents who donate and sell their discarded clothing, other clothing items and textiles, as well as residents who volunteer and otherwise contribute to activities to reduce excess consumption.	
CHALLENGE	The challenge is to identify a comprehensive (physical and digital) C2B, C2B2C, and B2B solution that allows to meet the needs of various stakeholders – consumers, clothing brands, retailers and providers of relevant service providers to participate comfortably in the circular economy .	
SOLUTION	The TEXTALE client loyalty platform is designed for purchasing goods and services through TEXTALE's online and physical outlets, partner stores, and service outlets, offering special discounts and the possibility to pay with accumulated points. TEXTALE platform serves as an integrated Circular Economy solution encompassing activities from selling/donating to cleaning and repairing clothing and other textile items, reselling/ordering other essential services.	
NEXT STEPS	The Seeker is working with a team of IT and marketing experts and is seeking funding to complete, test and implement the TEXTALE platform Solution.	
IMPACT	TEXTALE one stop shop means new opportunities for the environment and people. The impact of this social innovation will be the normalization of Circular Economy practices and mainstreaming them into everyday lives of Lithuanians. Moreover, it will transform society's attitudes towards fashion.	

Table 12. Factsheet 2 - Lithuania

Factsheet 3 - Digital Band

SEEKER	NAME: MB Syvas	TYPE: Social Enterprise
	URL: https://syvas.lt/	CONTACT: Rasa Valinskiene
	MISSION: Preserve the cultural heritage of Skuodas, the Samogitian region. The syvas.lt e-shop sells handmade products and tools made by folk artists, craftsmen and senior citizens of the region.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Senior population of the Samogitian region.	
CHALLENGE	Addressing the gap between an aging population that preserved cultural heritage and craftsmanship, and a younger generation lacking in hands-on skills and finger dexterity needed to learn these crafts from artisans. Pupils of grades 5-9 growing up with digital technologies, has led to a decline in their ability to create intricate and essential handmade items.	
SOLUTION	A digital solution that would serve as a bridge between the old experience (seniors) and the future tradition-keepers (children, young people). The app users will be primary, technology, art and ethno-culture teachers who will innovate combining digital and real-world skills and will commit to make their students feel good about where they live. The app aims to empower students in grades 5-9, a generation growing up with digital technologies but moving away from hands-on skills that require finger dexterity.	
NEXT STEPS	The further development and implementation of this innovation will take place in the format of the SB2G business model, i.e. in partnership with the local authorities responsible for education.	
IMPACT	The social innovation will help SYVAS to expand their range of services and create an impact in local communities through formal and non-formal education activities, productive engagement of seniors and intergenerational bridge-building.	

Table 13. Factsheet 3 - Lithuania

Factsheet 4 - Easy Count

SEEKER	NAME: MB Solidari erdvė „Solidarumo kava“	TYPE: Small Partnership
	URL: https://www.facebook.com/Solidarikava	CONTACT: Ieva Karulaitienė
	MISSION: The social business is dedicated to integrating individuals with intellectual disabilities into the labor market by operating a mobile coffee bar across Lithuania with a coffee tricycle. Hot drinks and delicious desserts are served to provide a tasting experience and promote the message that individuals with disabilities are equal participants, uniquely special in their own right.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Youth with intellectual disability.	
CHALLENGE	A team of baristas with intellectual disabilities encounters difficulty in accurately returning change to customers who pay in cash. The need is for a semi-automated system (not self-checkout) that supports these young baristas to interact with clients and handle transactions effectively.	
SOLUTION	The solution consists of a digital cash change calculator which helps to identify and count cash. Such a solution empowers and enables a person with intellectual disability to be independent in "live" sales and cash handling without "taking them out of the equation".	
NEXT STEPS	The further development and implementation of this innovation will take place in the format of the SB2G business model, i.e. in partnership with the local authorities responsible for youth labor integration. The next steps include using the solution in stationery and mobile cafés.	
IMPACT	The solution prevents the risk of replacing baristas with a self-checkout counter. The primary impact is that workers with disabilities can participate in the entire service process while maintaining independence in task execution, supported by technology.	

Table 14. Factsheet 4 - Lithuania

Factsheet 5 - “SP Club” Beneficiary Relations & Impact Management

SEEKER	NAME: Senjorų Pasaulis (SP)	TYPE: Community organization, social enterprise
	URL: https://senjorupasaulis.lt/	CONTACT: Vida & Živilė
	MISSION: To provide virtual space for learning and socializing for those senior citizens who want to develop their skills and spend time in a meaningful way.	
	TARGET GROUPS: Seniors. SP Club Membership has 3 tiers of benefits. In the SP Club, everyone can participate in 4 modules: IT, languages, wellness and culture, attend events and outings, make new friends, share their experiences and knowledge.	
CHALLENGE	Currently, beneficiaries, namely seniors, lack real-time visibility into their breakthroughs, achievements and milestones of their senior citizen journey. “SP Club” needs to provide them with a tool for (i) track the progress of peers within their SP community using a game-based system, (ii) finding volunteering opportunities (e-mailing tool integration is needed), and (iii) provide a dashboard for celebrating their achievements alongside those of others within the "SP Club" community.	
SOLUTION	A system to engage beneficiaries, monitor their progress, make usage of benefits, identify challenges, develop steps, and to help seniors to keep being involved.	
NEXT STEPS	There is the idea to implement an “SP Achievement Booklet” which should help the organization measuring the business social impact: to count the number of hours of learning and activities, to measure seniors' satisfaction with the activities, etc.	
IMPACT	The solution allows for achieving a twofold objective: firstly, seniors will have a simple tool (“interface”) to provide feedback to the social enterprise that runs “SP Club”; second, through the “back office” of the solution (tool) the social enterprise will obtain data for assessing its social impact and monitoring its advances toward fulfillment of its mission.	

Table 15. Factsheet 5 - Lithuania